

Supplementary Data

Contina, A., A. K. Pierce, S. W. Yanco, E. S. Bridge, J. F. Kelly, and M. B. Wunder. 2022. Application of stable isotopes to study movement ecology and diet variation in a migratory songbird. *Journal of Field Ornithology*. Accepted. <https://journal.afonet.org/volXX/issYY/artZZ/>

Individual posterior probability assignment maps for group G1 including $\delta^2\text{H}_f$ values ranging from -175.6‰ to -160.2‰ ($M = -167.1\%$, $SD = 5.02\%$, $N = 18$). The red dot on the map represents the sampling site in Oklahoma.

Individual posterior probability assignment maps for group G2 including $\delta^2\text{H}_f$ values ranging from -159.3‰ to -150.4‰ (M = -154.9‰, SD 3.17‰, N = 23). The red dot on the map represents the sampling site in Oklahoma.

Individual posterior probability assignment maps for group G3 including $\delta^2\text{H}_f$ values ranging from -149.8‰ to -140.1‰ ($M = -145.4\text{‰}$, $SD = 2.88\text{‰}$, $N = 19$). The red dot on the map represents the sampling site in Oklahoma.

Individual posterior probability assignment maps for group G4 including $\delta^2\text{H}_f$ values ranging from -139.3‰ to -118.6‰ (M = -130.4‰, SD = 6.39‰, N = 16). The red dot on the map represents the sampling site in Oklahoma.